

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART VIII. RESOLUTION OF COBALTIC TRISBIGUANIDE COMPLEX INTO ITS OPTICALLY ACTIVE ENANTIOMERIDES.

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Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride has been resolved into its optically active enantiomerides by combining with *d*-tartaric acid and *d*-camphorsulphonic acid. The diastereoisomerides, chloro-*d*-tartrate, *d*-tartrate and *d*-camphorsulphonate of the *laevo* and *dextro* cobaltic trisbiguanide base, have been prepared in the pure state. The *l*-salt in all cases is less soluble.

A solution of the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex base deposited crystals of only the *laevogyrate* on fractional crystallisation in the cold till the entire solution was dried up. This is possibly the first instance of a complex inorganic salt manifesting the phenomenon of "*asymmetric transformation of the second order*" as described by Kuhn. Further evidence on the point is furnished by the study of the "*addition curve*" obtained by gradually adding the racemoid base to a solution of *dextro*-tartaric acid and observing the rotation after each addition. It has been shown that in a solution of the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex there is an equilibrium between the *dextro* and the *laevo* salt with the former in slight excess. From the slight *dextro*-rotatory mother-liquor after the separation of the first crop of *laevogyrate* from a solution of chloro-*d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex, pure *dextrogyrate* was obtained by repeated fractional precipitation with alcohol. A change in the external condition by changing the nature of the solvent helped to isolate the pure *d*-salt, which could not be obtained from aqueous solution.

A solution of the *d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex, though exhibiting asymmetric transformation, can, however, be normally fractionated giving pure *laevo*- and *dextrogyrates* as the least and the most soluble fractions respectively, due to favourable solubility and stability relationship.

From the pure *laevo*- and *dextrogyrate* of the chloro-*d*-tartrate, pure optically active enantiomerides of the sulphate, chloride and nitrate of the complex base were prepared. Their molecular rotations were quite high, suggesting an unsymmetrical co-ordination of the otherwise symmetrical biguanide molecules around the central atom, as was assumed by Rây and Saha in the first paper of the series.

In a previous communication of this series an account of the preparation and properties of cobaltic trisbiguanidine and its various salts was given (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 62). The constitution of biguanide complexes with trivalent metals like chromium and cobalt has also been thoroughly discussed in the first paper of the series (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670). Biguanide, like ethylenediamine, is a base, and a stronger base too, and it has been shown before (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*) that it serves as a "chelate" or bidentate molecule like the latter. It differs, however, from ethylenediamine in certain other respects.

In the first place, unlike ethylenediamine it does not behave as a neutral group or pseudo-base during co-ordination, but, on the other hand, acts as having an *aci*-group in the molecule in spite of its strong basic character. Consequently, it gives rise to the formation of hexa-co-ordinated inner complex salts with trivalent chromium and cobalt. The inner metallic complexes, thus formed, are not non-electrolyte though the primary valencies of the metal ions are fully satisfied. Due to the presence of a free amino-group in each biguanide molecule even after co-ordination, an inner metallic complex salt of the *second order* of a special kind is thereby produced, which makes the co-ordinated chromium or cobalt complex a trivalent cation. Secondly, though like ethylenediamine, its molecule by itself is symmetrically constituted, still it co-ordinates with the metal atom in an unsymmetrical manner (*cf.* Rāy and Saha, *loc. cit.*).

Like *tris*ethylenediamine complexes, the *tris*biguanide complexes also possess no plane or centre of symmetry and hence are resolvable into their optically active antipodes, as represented by the following structures (Fig. 1).

[Big H = one biguanide molecule.]

molecule as mentioned above.

An attempt to resolve the chromium *tris*biguanide salts, as stated before (Rāy and Dutt, *loc. cit.*), did not succeed well under usual circumstances, when combined with an active acid like *d*-tartaric acid, due to their more or less rapid hydrolysis into *bis*biguanide derivatives. The cobaltic *tris*biguanide complexes, being on the other hand quite stable, have been successfully split up into their enantiomorphous isomerides; the preparation and properties of the latter, as well as of their *diastereoisomerides* and of the corresponding partial racemates, are described in the present paper.

The resolution was accomplished by combining the complex ion either with *d*-tartaric acid in the form of *d*-tartrate or chloro-*d*-tartrate, or with *d*-camphorsulphonic acid.

An anomalous observation was, however, made during the fractional crystallisation of the chloro-*d*-tartrate. On allowing a solution of the

chloro-*d*-tartrate of the racemoid complex to crystallise slowly at the room temperature, the first crop of crystals, that separated from the solution, was found to be *laevo*-rotatory with $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -335^\circ$. This retained its rotation unchanged on further fractionation, proving that it is the pure *laevogyrate* of the *diastereoisomerides*. This evidently contradicts Werner's generalisation regarding the comparative solubility of chloro-*d*-tartrates of the optically active antipodes of cobaltic complexes (Werner, *Ber.*, 1912, 46, 865), which assumes that the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the *d*-cobaltic complex always forms the less soluble variety. Observations have also been made by Jaeger showing that Werner's conclusion in this respect is erroneous (*cf.* Jaeger, "Spatial Arrangement of Atomic Systems and Optical Activity," McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., 1930, p. 92). There is, therefore, no direct relationship between the configuration of the molecules and their relative or absolute solubility. The mother liquor from the first crop of crystals was found to be *dextro*-rotatory, but when allowed to crystallise deposited successive crops of only the *laevo*-isomeride till the entire solution was practically dried up. There is thus a continuous transformation in solution from the *dextro*- to the less soluble *laevo*-variety as represented below :

Both the *diastereoisomerides* were formed in equal amounts in solution to begin with and tend to approach an equilibrium as they are mutually interconvertible ; but before the kinetic equilibrium is established, the less soluble *laevo*-salt separates out from the solution. This ultimately leads to a complete conversion of the *dextro*- into the *laevo*-salt. An explanation of the anomaly can thus be offered.

Similar phenomenon was already observed in the case of many organic compounds and was named by Kuhn (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 49) as "*asymmetric transformation of the second order.*" According to Kuhn a "*first order transformation*" is one in which neither of the two interconvertible *diastereoisomerides* separates out from the solution but may exist in the latter in different proportions :

Jamison and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1646) have recently shown that a study of the "addition curve," as named by them, which expresses the rotation as a function of the acid : base ratio, serves as a reliable means of investigating the phenomenon of asymmetric transformation.

In the present case as well, it was noticed that by the gradual addition of the racemic base to a solution of the *d*-tartaric acid the rotation of the latter abnormally increased till an equivalent amount was added, after which

the further addition of the base decreased the rotation. The addition curve, thus obtained, is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2.

The form of the addition curve I (Fig. 2) furnishes a distinct evidence of the asymmetric transformation occurring in the solution of cobaltic *trisbiguanide-d-tartrate*.

Curve II (Fig. 2), obtained by the gradual addition of cobaltic hexammine carbonate to a solution of *d-tartaric acid*, has also been added to account for the influence of salt formation on the rotation of the acid. This effect is negative here and reduces the rotation. A 0.5% solution of tartaric acid was used in these experiments and this was taken to represent unit equivalent for the acid.

The chloro-*d-tartrate* of the *dextro*-base was, however, obtained in the pure crystalline state from the *dextro*-rotatory mother-liquor after the separation of the first crop of the *laevo*-*diastereoisomeride* by immediate fractional precipitation with alcohol. This suggests that the equilibrium condition of the system corresponds to an excess of the *dextro*-gyrate and hence the product obtained by immediate precipitation with alcohol, in which both the *diastereoisomerides* are insoluble, contains an excess of the complex *dextro*-salt. The isolation of the pure *dextrogyrate* from this by fractional precipitation with alcohol is indicative of the slow rate of transformation in solution leading to an equilibrium. This has been actually verified by experiments. For the slight *dextro*-rotation of a freshly prepared solution of the chloro-*d-tartrate* of the racemoid has been found to

increase gradually with time to a constant maximum value. This same equilibrium rotation was also arrived at starting from a solution of the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the laevo-rotatory as well as of the dextro-rotatory complex. Thus, approaching from three different directions the same equilibrium rotation $[\alpha]_D^{46.1} = +14^\circ$ was obtained. The concentration of the solution employed was 1% in all cases. The corresponding value at 25° determined from the partial racemate was $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +31^\circ$. The initial specific rotation of a freshly prepared solution of the partial racemate was found to be $[\alpha]_D = +6^\circ$ only, the temperature effect on its rotation is practically negligible and lies within the limits of experimental errors. $[\alpha]_D^{46.1}$ for the pure *dextro*-diastereoisomeride is equal to 340° . The equilibrium composition calculated from the above values is 51.2% *d*-salt and 48.8% *l*-salt at 46.1° and the equilibrium constant K at the same temperature is equal to 1.049. Similarly the equilibrium composition at 25° is 53.75% *d*-salt and 46.25% *l*-salt, and $K_{25} = 1.1622$. From the values of K at the two temperatures, the heat evolved in the transformation is calculated according to van't Hoff's equation. This gives a value of 923 calories. The transformation process (*l*-salt $\rightarrow$ *d*-salt) is, therefore, an exothermic one and K decreases with temperature. The free energy decrease of the system in this transformation, ΔF , is thus 30.4 calories at 46.1° and 89.1 calories at 25° . In conformity with the greater stability of the *dextro*-salt, a solution of the latter requires about 9 days to reach the equilibrium rotation value at 46.1° , for which the *laevo*-salt requires about 7 days.

The pure *diastereoisomerides* are quite stable but lose their water and become anhydrous at 62° without any change in their optical activity. The activity remains unchanged even when they are heated to 105° . The partial racemate, like the active isomerides also becomes anhydrous at 62° .

No anomaly was, however, observed when the complex racemate was split up by means of *d*-tartaric acid in the form of pure tartrate or by *d*-camphorsulphonic acid. The two *diastereoisomerides* separated normally in these cases during fractional crystallisation—here also the laevogyrate being less soluble, separated out first. That the *dextro*- and the *laevo*-salt can thus be obtained in the pure state in spite of their interconvertibility leading to an equilibrium indicates a more favourable solubility and stability relationship (*i.e.* a comparatively less difference in solubility and a slower transformation rate).

From the two *diastereoisomerides*, thus prepared, the pure optically active enantiomorphous isomerides of the chloride, sulphate and nitrate of the complex base were obtained with specific and molecular rotations of $[\alpha]_D^{21} = \pm 450^\circ$, $\pm 362.5^\circ$, $\pm 388^\circ$, and $[M]_D^{21} = \pm 2105^\circ$, $\pm 2062^\circ$, and

$\pm 2125^\circ$ respectively. The corresponding values for the chloride and nitrate of the complex cobalt *tris*ethylenediamine base are $[M]_D = \pm 608^\circ$ and $\pm 562^\circ$ only. A higher rotation for the complex cobaltic *tris*biguanidinium ion, compared to that of *tris*ethylenediamine cobaltic ion, is indicative of a lower degree of symmetry for the former. This furnishes an indirect evidence in support of the constitution of *tris*biguanide complexes (an unsymmetrical co-ordination of the symmetrical biguanide molecules) as suggested by Rây and Saha (*loc. cit.*).

The optically active antipodes of the cobaltic *tris*biguanide ion in all cases (chloride, sulphate and nitrate) are quite stable in the solid state and retain their rotation unchanged even up to a temperature of 105° . In aqueous solution they can be maintained without any change up to a temperature of 35° for over 12 hours. At about 40° they show slow racemisation in solution, which becomes almost instantaneous at the boiling temperature. Dilute solutions of alkalis also bring about rapid racemisation, acids in somewhat larger concentration react in the same way.

A detailed study of the kinetics of interconversion of the active diastereoisomerides, the velocity of racemisation of the pure active enantiomerides and the catalytic effect of many simple and complex ions upon it, as well as the nature of the change associated with the phenomenon of racemisation will form the subject of a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Racemic Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloro-d-tartrate :

This was prepared by the double decomposition of the complex cobaltic *tris*biguanidinium chloride (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) with one molecule of silver *d*-tartrate. The solution, filtered from the silver chloride, was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The crystals were kept in air, till their weight became constant.

The substance forms orange-yellow, silky, rectangular plates, moderately soluble in water. When heated to 62° , the crystals lose their water and

become anhydrous. (Found : Cl, 5'45 ; Co, 9'30. Calc. : Cl, 5'50 ; Co, 9'28 per cent).

l-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloro-d-tartrate.—The laevogyrate was obtained in the form of orange-coloured, silky, thin rectangular plates by the fractional crystallisation of the above described partial racemate. The crop of crystals, that separated at the laboratory temperature, formed the pure *laevo*-salt. From a cold saturated solution of the racemate, the first crop separated on keeping only for a few hours. The crystals were filtered, washed first with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. (Found : Cl, 5'45 ; Co, 9'41. Calc. : Cl, 5'50 ; Co, 9'28 per cent).

It possesses the same composition as the partial racemate and loses all its water when heated to 62° without any change in its activity.

$$[\alpha]_D^{21} = -335^\circ. \quad [M]_D^{21} = -2129^\circ.$$

It retains its activity unchanged even when heated to 105° for hours.

d-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloro-d-tartrate.—The mother-liquor from the above described *laevo*-salt was at once subjected to fractional precipitation by means of alcohol. After removing several crops of crystals, till there was no further appreciable increase in the dextro-rotation of the separated solid, the residual liquor was completely precipitated with alcohol. The final precipitate was redissolved in cold water and again fractionally precipitated with alcohol. The process was repeated with the most soluble fraction in each case until the rotation of the finally separated product became maximum and constant.

It forms orange-coloured, irregular thick plates, highly soluble in water. (Found : Cl, 5'51 ; Co, 9'40. Calc. : Cl, 5'50 ; Co, 9'28 per cent).

It possesses the same composition as the *l*-salt and like the latter becomes anhydrous at 62°.

$$[\alpha]_D^{21} = +340^\circ. \quad [M]_D^{21} = +2161^\circ.$$

In all other respects it resembles the *laevo*-salt.

d-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Sulphate d-[Co(BigH⁺)₃]₂(SO₄)₂·7H₂O.

The complex *dextro*-sulphate was obtained as sparingly soluble, orange-coloured, prismatic needles from the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the *dextro* complex by precipitation with a cold saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in air. (Found : S, 8'42 ; Co, 10'41. Calc. : S, 8'44 ; Co, 10'37 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +362'5^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = +4125^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Sulphate.—The *laevo*-sulphate was obtained in a similar manner like its *dextro*-isomeride from the chloro-*d*-tartrate of the *laevo*-complex. It possesses the similar composition and properties as its *dextro*-analogue. (Found : S, 8'42 ; Co, 10'35. Calc.: S, 8'44 ; Co, 10'37 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -362.5^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = -4125^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloride : $d\text{-[Co(BigH}^+)_3]\text{Cl}_2$.—For its preparation the above described *d*-sulphate was digested in the cold with a saturated solution of the calculated quantity of barium chloride. The filtrate from barium sulphate was then evaporated to dryness in *vacuo*. The *dextro*-chloride forms readily soluble, orange-coloured crystals, appearing as rectangular prisms under the microscope. (Found : Co, 12'63. Calc. : Co, 12'59 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +450^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = +2108^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloride.—The *l*-chloride was obtained like its *d*-isomeride from the *l*-sulphate and barium chloride. It forms orange-coloured, prismatic crystals, very soluble in water and has the same composition as its *d*-analogue. (Found : Co, 12'62. Calc. : Co, 12'59 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -449^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = -2103^\circ$.

It can be heated to 105° without any change in its activity.

d-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Nitrate : $d\text{-[Co(BigH}^+)_3]\text{(NO}_3)_3$.—This was obtained like the previous compounds from the *d*-sulphate and barium nitrate. It forms orange-coloured prisms, soluble in water. Found : Co, 10'95. Calc. : Co, 10'77 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +388^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = +2126^\circ$.

l-Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium nitrate was prepared like its *d*-isomeride from the *l*-sulphate and barium nitrate. It forms moderately soluble, reddish yellow, irregular prisms and has the same composition as its *d*-analogue. (Found : Co, 10'90. Calc. : Co, 10'77 per cent).

l-Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium *d*-Camphorsulphonate : $l\text{-[Co(BigH}^+)_3]\text{d-(C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{O(SO}_3)_3}$.—This was obtained by the fractional crystallisation in the cold of the corresponding partial racemate previously described (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). The first crop of crystals obtained was further fractionated, always using the least soluble fraction, till two such fractions of two consecutive operations showed identical maximum rotation. The substance forms flesh-coloured crystals, moderately soluble in water. They were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The crystals were dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . (Found : Co, 5'71. Calc.: Co, 5'61 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -202$. $[M]_D^{21} = -2131^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium *d*-camphorsulphonate was prepared by the fractional crystallisation in the cold of the mother-liquor remaining after the separation of the first crop of crystals from a saturated

aqueous solution of the corresponding partial racemate. After several successive fractions were rejected, the solution finally deposited a strongly dextro-rotatory solid. This was purified by repeated crystallisation. It possesses the same composition as its *l*-analogue. (Found : Co, 5·70. Calc. : Co, 5·61 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +202^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = +2131^\circ$.

Racemic cobaltic trisbiguanidinium d-tartrate, $\tau[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 \cdot d\text{-(C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by digesting the solid base in the cold with a saturated solution of *d*-tartaric acid. The orange-coloured crystals of the tartrate were filtered, washed first with cold water and then with alcohol. They were afterwards dried in air. (Found : C, 22·81 ; H, 5·21 ; Co, 9·41. Calc. : C, 22·89 ; H, 5·09 ; Co, 9·38 per cent).

l-Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium d-Tartrate.—*Dextro*-tartrate of the *laevo*-complex was obtained by the fractional crystallisation of a saturated solution of the above described partial racemate. The first crop of crystals obtained was subjected to further fractionation, always employing the least soluble fraction for the purpose, till two consecutive fractions gave a maximum identical rotation. It resembles the partial racemate in properties and possesses the same composition. (Found : C, 22·75 ; H, 5·15 ; Co, 9·40. Calc. : C, 22·89 ; H, 5·09 ; Co, 9·38 per cent). $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -330^\circ$. $[M]_D^{21} = -4151^\circ$.

d-Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium d-tartrate was prepared by fractional crystallisation from the mother-liquor remaining after the separation of the first crop of crystals in the preparation of the *l*-salt from a solution of the partial racemate as described above. After several successive fractions were rejected, the solution finally deposited a strongly dextro-rotatory solid. This was then purified by repeated crystallisation. It possesses the same composition as its *l*-analogue. $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +332$. $[M]_D^{21} = +4176^\circ$.

All measurements were made in a Franz Schmidt and Haensch's polarimeter with a trisected field of vision and provided with an electrical heating arrangement by which the temperature could be maintained constant to $\pm 0\cdot1^\circ$.

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